

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1552229>

Abstract. *In this article today, the focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organizing students whose educational activities are optimally compatible with the goal of personality development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been increasingly raised.*

Key words: *English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.*

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and his own inner world.

Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organizing educational activities of students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been increasingly raised. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practically master a foreign language.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for each student to practically master the language, to choose such teaching methods that will allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching foreign languages.

Modern pedagogical technologies, such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, provide individualization and differentiation of teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning. Forms of work with computer teaching programs in foreign language lessons include: learning vocabulary; practicing pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; developing grammatical phenomena.

In English lessons, a number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet: the formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishing students' vocabulary; forming students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at exploring the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the horizons of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relationships and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in tests, quizzes, competitions, Olympiads held on the Internet, participate in correspondence with peers in other countries, chats, video conferences, etc.

Currently, priority is given to the issues of communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy and humanism of education.

These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of foreign language teaching is to teach free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond in various situations, i.e. communication. Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (this is the so-called principle of communicative authenticity). New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error. The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication, aimed at consciously perceiving the material and ways of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic readiness for communication.

Implementing a communicative approach on the Internet is not particularly difficult for the user. The communicative task should offer students a problem or question to discuss, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows us to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently select linguistic units to form their own opinions. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its goal is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is the creation of interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in methodology.

Interactivity is "the unification, coordination and complementation of actions in the communicative goal and result using speech tools". By teaching a real language, the Internet helps to form speech abilities and skills, and also ensures sincere interest in teaching vocabulary and grammar, and therefore efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond to them adequately in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered learning is the project method as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with mixed projects, which have research projects, creative, practice-oriented and informational characters. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate fosters such moral values as mutual assistance and empathy, forms creativity and activates students. In general, in the process of project learning, the inseparability of teaching and upbringing is observed.

The project method develops students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to concisely and easily formulate thoughts, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from various sources, processes them using modern computer technologies, creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need.

The introduction of information technologies into education significantly diversifies the process of perceiving and processing information. Thanks to computers, the Internet and multimedia, students have a unique opportunity to assimilate a large amount of information with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also significantly expanding. In the conditions of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and hold teleconferences themselves.

The main criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology are tests. The priority of this technology is to redirect the educational process from the teacher to the student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his cognitive activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills in independently assimilating information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

REFERENCES

1. Halikova, L. U. (2021). THE THEORETICAL BASES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE IS TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY. *Международный научш-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА»*. Выпуск № 25 (том 2)(июнь, 2021). Дата въ^да в свет: 30.06. 2021., 109.SJIF 2023 = 6.131 / ASI Factor = 1.73(1/2), Jan., 2023 https://www.mpcareer.ru/_files/ugd/a62191_102fd91a032e413891a72621802b89f4.pdf#page=109
2. Халикова, Л. У., & Абдураззаков, Ш. А. У. (2021). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ МОТИВАЦИИ У СТУДЕНТОВ НЕЯЗЫКОВЫХ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТЕЙ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Academy*, (6 (69)), 43-44. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/formirovanie-motivatsii-u-studentov-neyazykovyh-spetsialnostey-pri-izuchenii-angliyskogo-yazyka>

3. Uktamovna, X. L. (2021). TEACHING COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGES. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 2(6), 53-56. <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/1896..>
- Yuldasheva, M. B. (2020). HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH UZBEK TRANSLATION. Theoretical & Applied Science, (3), 11-14.